

AUTOMATED WATER BOTTLE PACKAGING SYSTEM

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Abstract

With the rise of variability in manufacturing, the necessity for flexibility in automation is increasing in significance. Be it with small or large companies, it is important to be able to save resources where possible and eliminate costs for things that quickly become obsolete on the assembly line. With the improvements in robotics technology, it has become simpler to use robots with specialized attachments and replace dedicated assembly machinery in manufacturing settings. The goal of this study was to demonstrate the efficacy of replacing current superfluous, expensive machinery with robotic arms via the design and assembly of an automated water bottle packaging system that uses devices and materials found on site. In this paper, the authors detail project goals, specifications, and deliverables, as well as the complete design of the system. Also presented are the calculations and testing procedures used for the project design and details of the project schedule and budget.

Introduction

The purpose of this project was to provide a conceptual framework of how a robotic arm can be used to replace the necessity for dedicated machinery in packaging warehouses. In this paper, the authors provide measurable goals and specifications, project deliverables, methodology, theoretical background, design, chronological outline, and costs for the design. During the initial phases of the robot's programming, it was able to pick up a box that would then be filled with bottles, sealed within the box, and returned to the starting point. This would usually take a three-step process involving a lengthy conveyor track, a bottle placing unit, and a box packaging machine. This all would take an excessive amount of space and resources to accomplish, when compared to the simpler costs of a single robot that, in a changing environment, can be flexible enough to change with it.

Project Goals

The creation of this robotic packaging line had the following goals.

- Create an efficient water bottle packaging system,
- Easily pick-and-place bottles for packaging,
- Efficiently fold lids and seal boxes
- Control and monitor the system using an HMI panel.
- Develop a packaging system that allows easy maintenance.

Specifications

The specifications of the project are listed below.

- The HMI display will control the packaging system via virtual "START" and "STOP" buttons, as well as determine the number of packaged bottles and sealed boxes.
- Water bottles with a height of 4" and a diameter of 2.5" are placed at the starting point of the primary conveyor belt system manually.
- The bottle conveyor system will run at a constant speed of 6.6 bottles/min.
- An 8" x 8" x 5" cardboard box will be placed at the starting point of a secondary conveyor belt system.
- An optic/proximity sensor located at the end of the bottle-transporting conveyor belt and the box-transporting belt will be calibrated to detect an object at 0.5" from itself.
- A Fanuc robot will operate at a maximum speed of 225 mm/s.
- The robot will place nine bottles into the box before proceeding to the lid-folding and sealing step.
- Three-inch strips of double-sided tape will be placed onto the cardboard box flaps before placing them onto the conveyor.
- The pressure used for the pneumatic system is kept at 40 psi.
- The entire water bottle packaging cycle takes no more than four minutes to complete.

Deliverables

The deliverables of the project include:

- CAD models and drawings
- Calculations and analysis
- A project schedules
- A project budgets
- Testing data
- A completely built packaging system
- Risk assessment
- PLC programming
- Fanuc robot programming

Methodology

The design of the automated water bottle packaging system was completed with concepts taken from Advanced Instrumentation and Automation for Filling and Packaging of Beverages (Development of an Educational Robot Vision System, 2012; Chatterjee, 2014). Figure 1 shows the calculations used to determine the total travel distance of the Fanuc robot during the bottle packaging process for one cycle, based on a simulated system created in SolidWorks. These travel-distance calculations helped determine an appropriate speed for bottle transportation via a conveyor line. Calculations were also used to determine the total power

consumption of the electrical components within the system, which were based on real-time measurements. Access to the equipment and machinery was granted by the technology department of Purdue University Northwest. Testing was conducted in steps during the assembly and programming phases to confirm the proper functioning of all electro-mechanical and pneumatic devices (Mikhail & Wang, 2020). Due to the low cost of required components and materials, the project was funded by project group members.

Figure 1. Complete system assembly model.

Each subassembly was a separate part of the packaging system with some interconnected components, such as the electrical and communication wiring between the robot and the Allen-Bradley trainer (Kwak & Mikhail, 2020).

Robot Work Cell Assembly

The robot work cell assembly consisted of an aluminum table and a Fanuc LR Mate 200iD/4S 6-axis robot. The aluminum table was a pre-built model with a length of 44", a width of 27.5", and a height of 35". The tabletop, with a thickness of 1.25", had 13 half-inch diameter holes on each side, spaced one inch apart. The holes were placed 1.25 inches from the edges of the table. The tabletop was used for mounting the robot as well as the custom packaging base, and acted as the work envelope of the packaging procedure. Figure 2 shows how the Fanuc robot was mounted onto the tabletop at a fixed position. The robot was placed about 5" from the left side and 9.5" from the back of the table. The robot was connected to its controller and teach pendant, which was placed underneath the tabletop. The robot was used to execute the packaging operations via pick-and-place and point-to-point motions.

Figure 2. Fanuc LR Mate 200 iD/4S robot on an aluminum table.

A custom 3D-printed gripper was attached to the pneumatic end tool located at the end of the robotic arm. Figure 3 shows the gripper composed of two mirrored jaw pieces with a large slot in front when assembled. The jaws of the gripper were designed to fit a one-inch-diameter cap of a standard 8 FL OZ water bottle. There was a small shelf at the bottom of the slot on both sides of the jaws to allow the bottle cap's lower ring to hook on when the gripper was closed.

Figure 3. Custom gripper model.

The robot used the gripper to direct a packaging box to and from the box conveyor line and across the packaging base as well as pick up the appropriate water bottles by the cap from the bottle conveyor line and then insert them into the packaged box. The gripper was also used to press and hold down the remaining back flap of the box during the lid-closing procedure.

Custom Packaging Base Assembly

Figure 4 shows a custom base with attached pneumatic cylinders that was designed and created to serve as a packaging zone for the system. The base platform was built out of 24" x 24" x 1/2" plywood, with the walls constructed from 1 1/2" x 3/4" wood blocks. There was an 8.5-inch-wide path that led from the right side of the board to an empty, encased

area that was designated to be the packaging location of the box, where it will travel to and from the box conveyor. The base pathway was designed to fit and align the packaged boxes during box movement. When a box was directed to the designated packaging zone, it would then be pressed up against the front wall. When packaging procedures were performed, the robot would shift the box through the same pathway and knot the box conveyor line located right from the base. Two 1/2-inch holes were made on the right side of the base to mount it onto the robot work cell table via 1/2-inch hex head cap bolts.

Figure 4. Pneumatic packaging base.

Three wooden support blocks were constructed and attached to the packaging slot walls with wood screws, with each one being on a different side of the packaging area. The wooden support blocks were 9.25" in height with a 45° cut facing the front. A truss was used to support the vertical block and prevent it from breaking due to excessive forces. Figure 5 shows how, at the top of the 45° surface, a Bimba four-inch-stroke, double-acting pneumatic cylinder, was mounted into a D-129-cylinder bracket and attached to the support block with wood screws. The cylinders were mounted facing downward towards the packaging zone and positioned so the rods extended towards the center of the top surface of the box during the lid-folding procedure.

Figure 5. Bimba 094-DP pneumatic cylinder.

A PanelView Plus 1000 HMI was used to control and monitor the operations of the packaging system. The operator panel was designed in FactoryTalk View Studio and then uploaded into the physical device memory. The panel contained controls for the operator to start and stop the

packaging cycle, as well as clear the faults on all devices. There were numeric string displays to indicate the number of bottles and boxes packaged along with lights to indicate the state of the system.

The design of the main packaging operator panel contained the main controls of the system, the status indicator lights for system operations, and the displays for the number of packaged items.

There was a panel with five control pushbuttons located on the left side of the screen. The "Clear Faults" button was used to remove any faults present on both Powerflex 525 devices and the Fanuc 6-axis robot. After clearing the faults, the "Start" button could be pressed to start the packaging system, as it began the cycle and activated the robot programming. The "Stop" and "E-Stop" buttons were used to stop the conveyor systems and robot. The "Reset Count" button reset the number of packaged bottles and boxes.

In the center of the screen was a panel indicating system operations in which six indicator lights and two numeric displays were present. The six lights corresponded to the labeled system states and, when inactive, the lights would blink red. When the system item was active, the associated light would be green. The two numeric displays were used by the system to indicate the number of packaged items, which came from the ControlLogix PLC programming.

Programming

The programming designed for controlling the automated water bottle packaging system was broken down into two types. The first type was the teach pendant programming created to control the Fanuc 6-axis robot, as well as change the states of its digital inputs and outputs. The other type was the PLC programming done in Studio 5000 software to control, mediate, and monitor the involved Allen-Bradley devices, as well as to communicate with the robot.

Teach Pendant Programming

The main teach pendant programming would run when the packaging cycle was started. According to the program section in Table 1, the robot would wait in a jump-label loop until a box was detected by the sensor, which would change the state of the digital input "DI22" and allow the robot to continue.

Table 1. Robot main program.

<pre> 1: LBL (3) ; 2: IF (DI (22) =ON) THEN; 3: JMP LBL (2); 4: ENDIF; 5: JMP LBL (3); 6: LBL (2) </pre>
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When the robot progressed to line 6, the value of register R3 was set to zero, and the X and Y coordinate data of position register PR3 were reset. The robot then waited two seconds before traveling to the cardboard box via pick-and-place movement and then directing it to the packaging area via point-to-point movement. Table 2 shows that digital output DO30 then turned on, marking the beginning of the bottle packaging phase, and the program moved to the box packaging subroutine. The system remained in the bottle subprogram until all nine bottles were packaged.

Table 2. Robot main program 2 (Mikhail & Abad, 2021).

```

10: WAIT 2.00(sec);
11: J P [1] 50% FINE;
12: J P [2] 50% FINE;
13: L P [3] 200mm/sec FINE;
14: L P [4] 200mm/sec FINE;
15: L P [5] 200mm/sec FINE;
16: L P [6] 200mm/sec FINE;
17: L P [7] 200mm/sec FINE
18: L P [8] 200mm/sec FINE
19: L P [9] 150mm/sec FINE
20: J P [11] 50% FINE;
21: J P [7] 50% FINE;
22: DO [30] =ON;
23: LBL [1];
24: CALL AWP;
25: IFR [3] <=2, JMP LBL [1];

```

PLC Programming

The PLC programming created in Studio 5000 was used to control and mediate electrical signals between the devices of different subassemblies, such as the Allen-Bradley devices on the trainer panel or the solenoid valves on the pneumatic base. The PLC programming can be broken down into the main control program, box conveyor subprogram, bottle conveyor subprogram, and the CompactLogix subprogram.

Table 3 shows that in the main PLC program, downloaded into the ControlLogix controller, the two control subprograms for running the conveyor systems are active for as long as the program is running.

Table 3. Structured text PLC main program.

```

if Vk_RobotStart OR Run And Not Vk_RobotStop then;
Run: =1;
fanuc:O.Data[0].0:=1;
fanuc:O.Data[0].1 :=1;
fanuc:O.Data[0].2: =1;
fanuc:O.Data[0].7: =1;
TONR(T1_ST);
T1_ST. Reset: =0;
T1_ST. TimerEnable: =1;
T1_ST.PRE: =1000;
fanuc:O.Data[0].7: =T1_ST.TT;
TOFR(T2_ST);
T2_ST. Reset: =0;
T2_ST.TimerEnable:=1;
T2_ST.PRE: =1000;

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fanuc:O.Data[0].5: =T2_ST.TT;
else
Run: =0;
fanuc:O.Data[0].0: =0;
fanuc:O.Data[0].1: =0;
fanuc:O.Data[0].2: =0;
fanuc:O.Data[0].7: =0;
end_if;

```

Testing

Preliminary tests were done on-site to test the proper functioning of some of the individual system components. First, the conveyor system motor power cables were wired to the variable frequency drives, and then the Allen-Bradley trainer was turned on. Table 4 shows that after setting up the communication modules, a simple program for controlling the VFD outputs was created in Studio 5000, which was then downloaded into the 1756-L75 ControlLogix PLC. The program was activated, and then individual virtual inputs were toggled to momentarily energize the “clear faults,” “start,” “stop,” “forward,” and “reverse” VFD outputs. A move function was also used to send a value of 350 to the frequency command output of the VFD to adjust the speed of the motors.

Table 4 summarizes the results of the tests, the problems observed that resulted from them, and the actions taken to eliminate or mitigate the issues.

Table 4. Test results, problems, and solutions.

Test	#	Results	Problems	Remedies
Bottle Conveyor Control and Movement	6	conveyor line runs smoothly full control of conveyor starts and stop adjusted speed appropriate for transportation bottles do not fall over	None	None
Box Conveyor Control and Movement	4	conveyor line runs smoothly	Low-speed application	Powerflex frequency increased to 2000 for speed gain
Sensor and Solenoid Valve Produced-Consumed Tags	9	full control of conveyor starts stops, and bi-directional motion	None	None
Bottle Packaging Subroutine	17	initial speed too slow for the application	air tubes on the robot arm side drag onto the flap of the box,	air tubes are taped down to the arm of the robot

			causing additional tilting	
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Additional minor tests were conducted to verify the other operations of the packaging system, such as box lid folding and sealing, box transportation to and from the box conveyor line, and the operations of the HMI panel. Figure 6 shows that, for the box-folding application, boxes with unfolded lids were placed into the packaging zone and the cylinder rods were triggered to extend, thus observing if the lid could be closed properly by the pistons. As for the box transportation test, an empty and a full box were placed inside the pathway and the robot was briefly programmed to direct both boxes between the packaging area and the box conveyor line entrance point.

Figure 6. Packaging cycle testing preparations.

The fully automated water bottle packaging system was tested and validated after all modifications were completed. Figure 7 shows the complete setup (Gretsch, 2014).

Figure 7. Automated water bottle packaging system.

Calculations

The packaging time of the robot was then calculated by using the total sum of the travel distance taken by the gripper and the maximum robot speed in each mode, which was 225 mm/sec, and inserting both into the velocity defined by Equation 1:

$$S_t = S_o + 18S_p + 18S_D + 2\sum S_{a(1-9)} \quad (1)$$

where,

S_t is the total distance the robot gripper travels for bottles.

S_o is the distance from the gripper to the bottle approach point.

S_p is the distance from the bottle approach point to the bottle pick-up point.

S_D is the distance from the bottle placement approach point to the bottle destination point in box.

S_a is the distance between the bottle approach point to each bottle and the placement point above the box.

$$S_t = 725.68''$$

The calculated time was then utilized to obtain the packaging speed of the robot in bottles-per-minute via a ratio defined by Equation 2:

$$t_B = \frac{S_t}{V_t} = 81.8 \text{ sec} \quad (2)$$

where,

t_B is the bottle packaging time.

V_t is the maximum robot speed in teach mode.

The speed of the bottle conveyor line was calculated with an assumed time of 60 seconds for transporting the nine water bottles. The time was divided by the number of bottles to get the time required for one bottle to be transported. The resulting time was then used to calculate the speed of the conveyor belt, where the distance was the conveyor length of 28'', as defined by Equation 3:

$$V_B = \frac{S_B}{T_{SB}} \quad (3)$$

where,

V_B is the bottle conveyor speed.

S_B is the bottle conveyor line length (= 28'').

t_{SB} is the time of travel for single bottle (= 6.7 sec/bottle).

$$V_B = 4.18 \text{ in/sec}$$

Troubleshooting and Testing

Regarding troubleshooting, there were minimal issues encountered with the initial program. However, a significant problem was identified with the LIM function blocks, which were not functioning correctly. Fortunately, a quick online search and feedback from an instructor provided a solution. By inputting the low value into the low limit and the high value into the high limit, the function block could successfully verify if the test value was within the specified range. Conversely, if the low- and high-value inputs were swapped, with the low value assigned to the high-limit input and the high value assigned to the low-limit input, the function block would accurately determine if the test value fell outside the designated range.

Conclusions

The results of the project indicate that the custom automated water bottle packaging system was able to package a set of nine water bottles inside a cardboard box, fold down the lid, and seal the box shut. The bottles were easily picked up by the robot using the custom 3D-printed gripper. With the use of the pneumatic system, the box lid was folded down and kept shut, despite minor issues with one of the cylinder rods. The package lid was kept shut with the use of double-sided tape, fulfilling the sealing criteria of the project. With the assistance of the pneumatic cylinders, the Fanuc robot could transport the cardboard box to and from the box conveyor belt before and after the packaging procedures. The system was able to be run and stopped by the HMI panel controls, and the indicator lights lit up according to the state of the system. It was determined that the packaging cycle took almost the full four minutes to complete, with a robot auto mode speed at 50%; thus, with a higher setting, the cycle would take less time to complete.

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